

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

INFLUENCE OF SYNTHESIS METHODS ON PHOTOLUMINESCENCE PROPERTIES OF PP+PbS/CdS NANOCOMPOSITES

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Abstract

In the given paper, we studied the photoluminescence properties of PP+PbS/CdS nanocomposites synthesized with two different methods. It was found that the influence of synthesis methods can change the photoluminescence spectra of nanocomposites. The size of the nanoparticles produced by different synthesis methods varied as well. Nanocomposites have been analyzed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy. Photoluminescence (PL) analysis was carried out at room temperature, and it was determined that the obtained films have a broad emission spectra.

Keywords: photoluminescence, polypropylene, PbS, CdS, nanocomposites

Introduction

There are various methods to synthesize nanocomposites. The same nanocomposites can be synthesized by different methods. With the help of different synthesis methods, the properties of nanocomposites can be changed. The fabrication of polymer nanocomposites includes intercalation, in situ intercalative polymerization, melt intercalation, template synthesis, mixing, in situ polymerization, and the sol-gel process [1]. The size-dependent properties of semiconductor and polymer nanocomposites make these materials very attractive in terms of their possible application in various fields of technology such as optical switching, single electron transistors, solar cells, nonlinear optics, optoelectronic devices, and heterogeneous photocatalysis [2]. In our study of in-situ cation exchange, solubility methods were used to synthesize nanocomposites. Each method's photoluminescent properties were investigated. It was found that the photoluminescence spectra of nanocomposites changed the dependence of synthesis methods.

Synthesis of nanocomposites

The isotactic polypropylene (PP brand Sigma Aldrich P code 1001326963) has a density of 0.91 g/ml at 250 °C, a refractive index of $n_{20/D}$ 1.49, a transition temperature of T_g -26 °C, a mol.wt.-average M_w 250000 by GPC, an autoignition temperature of 674 °F, and a melting point of 1890. The images of the produced nanocomposites have been obtained by scanning electron microscopy (SEM; Jeol JSM-7600 F). The photoluminescent properties of nanocomposite films

were investigated using a Varian Cary Eclipse spectrofluorimeter in the 200–900 nm wavelength range.

1. Synthesis sorbsion techniques

To obtain PbS and CdS nanoparticles in a polymeric matrix, transition metal ions Pb^{2+} and Cd^{2+} were first sorbed into isotactic polypropylene powders. The production of hybrid nanocomposites PP+PbS/CdS occurs in subsequent stages: first, the synthesis of the nanocomposites PP/PbS and PP/CdS, respectively, and then the mixing of the two previously produced nanocomposites.

2. In-situ polymerization methods

In this method for synthesis PbS and CdS nanoparticles were first synthesized using this method. The following reactions occurred as a result of the synthesis of nanoparticles:

PP was solved in toluene, and the nanoparticles of PbS and CdS were added to the PP solution and was mixed with a magnetic stirrer for 2 h. Film samples of nanocomposite materials have been prepared by hot thermal pressing method.

Results and discussions

Figure 1 shows the photoluminescence spectra of PP+PbS/CdS nanocomposites synthesized by the sorbsion method. The graph shows that excitation wavelength ($E_x = 342$ nm) and luminescent observe in the 681-700 nm range.

Figure 1. Photoluminescence spectre of nanocomposites synthesized by sorbtion methods

Figure 2 shows the photoluminescent spectra of PP+PbS/CdS nanocomposites synthesized by in-situ polymerization methods. As can be seen from the graph, at the same conditions (Ex = 342 nm), luminissence intensity is very high. It is meant that in-

situ polymerization methods are a more optimal method for the photoluminescent properties of PP+PbS/CdS nanocomposites. This method also implies that the luminisence center is more active.

Figure 2. The photoluminescence spectral range of nanocomposites synthesized using various polymerization methods.

Figure 3 shows SEM images of PP+PbS/CdS nanocomposites synthesized by sorbsion and in-situ polymerization methods. The size of nanoparticles produced by sorbsion methods varies by (50-60) nm. The size of nanoparticles in other methods is very small, varying between 7 and 12 nm. In the second method, we used CTAB as a stabilization agent to aid

in the formation of small nanoparticles. Analyzing photoluminescence spectra of nanocomposites reveals that intensity changes externally. It can be expressed in terms of nanoparticle size. When two methods are compared, in-situ polymerization methods are found to be more effective for the photoluminescent properties of PP+PbS/CdS nanocomposites. .

Figure 3. SEM images of PP+PbS/CdS nanocomposites synthesized by different methods

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